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The first record of *Stylops thwaitesi* (Insecta: Strepsiptera: Stylopidae) in Ukraine

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Ostrovsky, A. M. First record of *Stylops thwaitesi* (Insecta: Strepsiptera: Stylopidae) in Ukraine. — The strepsipteran species *Stylops thwaitesi* Perkins, 1918 from the family Stylopidae found in Belichi (Ryiv Region) to parasitize in *Andrena (Taeniandrena) ovatula* (Kirby, 1802) in summer 2005 is new to the fauna of Ukraine. Brief information on distribution and ecology of this species is given.

Key words: *Stylops thwaitesi*, faunistics, Ukraine.

Островський, А. М. Перша знахідка *Stylops thwaitesi* Perkins, 1918 (Insecta: Strepsiptera: Stylopidae) в Україні. — Виялокриле *Stylops thwaitesi* Perkins, 1918, вид з родини Stylopidae, знайдений у Біличах (Київська обл.) на *Andrena (Taeniandrena) ovatula* (Kirby, 1802) влітку 2005 р., вперше зазначений для фауни України. Наведено дані щодо поширення та екології виду.

Ключові слова: *Stylops thwaitesi*, фауністика, Україна.

Островский, А. М. Первая находка *Stylops thwaitesi* (Insecta: Strepsiptera: Stylopidae) в Украине. — Веерокрылое *Stylops thwaitesi* Perkins, 1918, вид из семейства Stylopidae, найденный в Беличах (Киевская обл.) на *Andrena (Taeniandrena) ovatula* (Kirby, 1802) летом 2005 г., впервые отмечен для фауны Украины. Приведены данные по распространению и экологии вида.

Ключевые слова: *Stylops thwaitesi*, фаунистика, Украина.

Introduction

Members of the order Strepsiptera display highly peculiar morphology and lifestyles. They are small to medium-sized insects (1.0–7.5 mm long) exhibiting extreme sexual dimorphism (Kinzelbach, 1971; Kathirithamby, 1989). Free living and flying males have twisted hind wings, while their fore wings are reduced to club-like appendages. Usually endoparasitic and wingless females are known to colonize members of seven insect orders (Kathirithamby, 1989, 2009). Approximately 600 strepsipteran species are known to occur globally (Kathirithamby, 2002; Kinzelbach & Pohl, 2003), while 30 species from 7 families have been recorded by far from Europe (Pohl, 2010; Soon *et al.*, 2011).

The Strepsiptera fauna of Ukraine is still poorly known. By far, eight species have been recorded from

the country (Straka *et al.*, 2006, 2015; Pohl, 2010; Cook, 2019; Ogoł', 2020). While studying materials from the collection of Prof. Dr. Hab. Oleg Aleksandrowicz (Institute of Biology and Earth Sciences, Pomeranian University in Slupsk, Poland), a previously unrecorded species was identified in the specimens from Ukraine

Order Strepsiptera

Family Stylopidae

Stylops thwaitesi Perkins, 1918 (Figs 1–2)

Material examined. Ukraine, Kyiv vic., Bilychi, in ♀ *Andrena (Taeniandrena) ovatula* (Kirby, 1802) 14.06.2005 1♀, (M. Nesterov leg.) (A. Ostrovsky det.).

1

2

Figs 1–2. *Andrena (Taeniandrena) ovatula* (Kirby, 1802): ♀ stylized by a ♀ of *Stylops thwaitesi*: 1 — habitus, dorsal; 2 — abdomen, postero-dorsally (♀ of *S. thwaitesi* exerted at posterior border of gastral terga IV and V).

Distribution. Austria, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Russia, Spain, Switzerland, former Yugoslavia (Cook, 2019). Recently found in Belarus (Ostrovsky, 2021).

Hosts. *Stylops thwaitesi* is a typical parasite of many species of the genus *Andrena* Fabricius, 1775 (Hymenoptera: Apidae): *A. (T.) ovatula* (Kirby, 1802) (Perkins, 1918; Kifune *et al.*, 1994), *A. (T.) similis* Smith,

1849 (Hofeneder, 1939), *A. (T.) albofasciata* Thomson, 1870 (Pasteels, 1954; Günther & Šedivý, 1957), *A. (T.) ezoensis* Hirashima, 1965 (Kifune & Hirashima, 1985; Kifune & Maeta, 1990), *A. (T.) wilkella* (Kirby, 1802) (Luna de Carvalho, 1974; Pasteels, 1954; Günther & Šedivý, 1957), *A. (T.) intermedia* Thomson, 1870 and *A. (T.) lathyri* Alfken, 1899 (Smit *et al.*, 2020). From Ukraine, only *A. (T.) ovatula* has been recorded by far as its host. In Ukraine, *A. (T.) ovatula* is a widespread and common species.

Notes. *Stylops thwaitesi* has a complicated taxonomic history, which has been described in detail by Cook (2019) and can be briefly summarized as follows. Thwaites (1841, 1842) reported a species of *Stylops* that parasitized *A. convexiuscula* (= *A. ovatula*, which is currently recognized to be a host of *S. thwaitesi*, which is likely conspecific with the Thwaites' species). Saunders (1872) named the strepsipterans that parasitize *A. convexiuscula* as *S. thwaitesi* in recognition of Thwaites' discovery, but did not formally describe the species. Pasteels (1949) declared *S. thwaitesi* as *nomen nudum*. Perkins (1918) briefly described what he thought to be the strepsipteran mentioned by Thwaites (1841, 1842) and Saunders (1872). Perkins' brief description of *Stylops thwaitesi* was based on a specimen from *Andrena afzeliella* (= *A. ovatula*); he declared that the name he used is a corrected subsequent spelling of "*S. thwaitesi*". The name proposed by Perkins, however, is the first available and valid name of this species. Perkins (1918) also named *S. wilkella* for specimens previously recorded under *S. melittae*, which he stated was "extremely similar" to *S. thwaitesi* but used *A. wilkella* as a host. These species were later synonymized by Pasteels (1954). *Stylops albofasciata* Günther & Šedivý, 1957 parasitizing *Andrena albofasciata* (= *A. ovatula*) is now considered to be a junior synonym of *S. thwaitesi*. Kinzelbach (1978) considered *S. thwaitesi* and all European *Stylops* species as synonyms of *S. melittae*. Recently, Straka *et al.* (2015) have resurrected *S. thwaitesi* from synonymy, and considered *S. alfkeni* and *S. borealis* to be junior synonyms of *S. thwaitesi* instead. Cook (2019) considered *S. thwaitesi*, *S. alfkeni* and *S. borealis* to be separate species.

Conclusion

Stylops thwaitesi is formally recorded from Ukraine for the first time. Its only known host in Ukraine is *Andrena (Taeniandrena) ovatula*.

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